

The Influence of Music on Memory: Cognitive Mechanisms, Educational Applications, and Therapeutic Benefits

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Abstract: The interaction between music and memory has been of great interest in cognitive science and psychology, disclosing mechanisms through which auditory stimuli affect retention of information. This review presents recent research on the distinctive influence of music on short- and long-term, working, visual, auditory, and mechanical memory. Research suggests that music can enhance memory by improving concentration and mood. However, its influence varies depending on factors such as tempo, complexity, and familiarity. While music frequently facilitates memory and performing tasks, certain types of music may interfere with a person's ability to concentrate and engage their brain. It has also enhanced memory in both educational settings and therapeutic practices, which can be beneficial for both healthy individuals and those suffering from memory impairments. In addition, music therapy also shows promise in treating memory loss in patient populations, specifically those suffering from neurodegenerative diseases like Alzheimer's. The influence of music on memory is further modulated by individual differences, such as musical training and personal preferences. The present paper focuses on the potential use of music in educational systems and therapeutic interventions for improving cognitive health and memory retention in humans.

Keywords: Music, Memory, Cognitive Science, Auditory Stimuli, Memory Retention, Working Memory, Music Therapy, Neurodegenerative Diseases, Memory Impairment, Musical Training, Tempo, Cognitive Enhancement, Therapeutic Interventions, Individual Differences, Memory Encoding

Introduction

The connection between music and memory has intrigued cognitive science and psychology researchers for decades, revealing intricate mechanisms by which auditory stimulation influences the memory and recall of information. The human ear translates sound waves into electrical signals for auditory perception. The external ear collects the sound, the middle ear amplifies it via the ossicles, and the inner ear's cochlea changes the mechanical vibrations into neural impulses. This process involves hair cells that conduct mechano-electrical transduction, crucial in interpreting sound waves. Also, the inner ear houses another balance organ that detects spatial orientation and movements of the head: the vestibular system. Tonotopic organization of the cochlea allows for efficient discrimination between different frequencies to enable pitch.

The study of memory emphasizes the sophisticated structure and function that this ability provides for the brain to encode, store, and retrieve information. The hippocampus processes short-term memories into long-term memories, and the

prefrontal cortex supports working memory and decision-making. Most memories are thought to involve synaptic plasticity; a simple phenomenon called long-term potentiation (LTP) enhances neural circuits following repeated activation. Structural changes, such as dendritic growth and synaptic remodeling, provide a physical basis for the storage of memory, whereas molecular mechanisms, such as the activation of CREB (cAMP Response Element-Binding protein), control gene expression necessary to maintain these changes. Memories can be divided into two broad declarative categories, which include facts and events, and nondeclarative categories, including skills and habits, each of which activates different but overlapping neural networks.

This review integrates existing research to explain how music influences various forms of memory, such as short-term, long-term, working, visual, auditory, and mechanical memory, and to address the underlying factors that drive these effects.

Methods

A literature search was conducted for this review using databases such as PubMed and JSTOR. Keywords applied include those related to music and memory, auditory memory, verbal memory, and music therapy. Preference was given to peer-reviewed studies published in the last 15 years, with some older foundational research included. Articles were selected if they examined the influence of music on various forms of memory. Studies focusing strictly on mood or emotion without direct relevance to memory were excluded. The key triggering information, similar to study design, participant details, and findings, was then analyzed in order to identify emerging patterns and research gaps.

Influence of Music on Auditory Memory

The influence of music on auditory memory has been widely investigated, with some very striking effects of music found on cognitive functioning. Evidence suggests that musical training benefits auditory working memory—that is, the ability to hold and manipulate auditory information briefly. For example, Nie et al. (2022) followed school-aged children undergoing music training over a period of one year in a longitudinal design. The study found improvements in children's memory following the training on the digit span backward task, their ability to remember sequences of numbers in reverse order, a measure of their central executive component of working memory, improved after receiving music training compared to before. Improvement here was significant and was not observed in children who underwent second-language training or no training at all. The particular assignment assesses the capacity of working memory to manipulate and rearrange information, signifying improved cognitive processing. Results of this nature have special interest for instructional methods of children's cognitive development.

Besides enhancing working memory, music also has an effect on context-dependent memory. Smith (1985) investigated the effects of background music on memory recall and found that when the same music was presented during both learning and recall phases, participants exhibited enhanced memory performance. This effect, known as context-dependent memory, suggests that music might be a powerful environmental cue, which associates given pieces of information with auditory stimuli. Conversely, music mismatching or absence at recall has been shown to impair performance, indicating the specificity of these auditory cues. Our findings have several practical implications for learning environments, as consistent auditory contexts may aid memory retention and retrieval.

In general, music has a twofold function in auditory memory: it improves working memory through training, and it is also a very good contextual cue for memory retrieval. These insights show the versatility of music in shaping cognitive processes and thereby offering valuable tools for educational and therapeutic applications. Future research could investigate how different genres of music or varying levels of musical expertise might influence these effects, further deepening our understanding of the complex relationship between music and memory.

Influence of Music on Visual Memory

The general process of visual memory is complex, as the brain needs to encode, store, and later retrieve information in a particular form. It helps an organism with the recognition of objects, identification of faces, and even spatial layouts; it also contributes to learning and navigation. Long-term and short-term are two categories of visual memory. In the case of short-term visual memory, which retains images and spatial details momentarily, while long-term visual memory retains information over a longer period, enabling recognition and recall.

Research indicates that music can have an impact on visual memory through several processes. Giannouli et al. (2024) conducted a study investigating the impact of short-term listening to contrasting excerpts of music on visuospatial working memory in both older and younger adults. Participants listened to excerpts of music composed by Mozart, Vivaldi, and Glass prior to completing tests such as the Corsi blocks task-backwards and the visual patterns test. In fact, the findings indicated that classical music with defined structure significantly enhanced memory performance, especially in tasks requiring recall and manipulation of spatial sequences. The results showed that listening to music could modulate performance in visuospatial working memory, with variation depending on both the type of music and participant age.

Ren et al. (2024) conducted a study investigating the impact of familiarity and schema on music and its role in encoding visual sequence information. Participants received paired sequences of abstract forms and music and then completed a sequence recall test to assess whether familiarity and structure in music could act as a "temporal schema" for enhancing temporally sequenced information in visual form. This effect was particularly strong when the music followed predictable patterns, reinforcing the fact that structured auditory cues can support visual memory retention. The results showed that both familiarity and structure in music could enable encoding for sequences of forms, and therefore, that structure in music helps organize and remember information in a visual format.

Influence of Music on Verbal Memory

Verbal memory, defined as the ability to encode, store, and retrieve words and language-based information, is something fundamental to human cognition. More recent research has examined diverse factors influencing verbal memory performance, with particular attention to the impact of music and the function of specific neural mechanisms.

Ferreri and Verga (2016) investigated the effects of music on verbal learning and memory. Their study showed that musical accompaniment during the learning phase of a language can improve verbal memory performance. Participants exposed to sung lyrics showed a better recall compared to those who learned the same material through spoken word alone. These findings suggest that the melodic and rhythmic elements in music may aid encoding and retrieval procedures in verbal memory.

An additional study by Thaut et al. indicated that music helps people remember words better. This happens because it makes recalling words easier and helps keep them in order. In the study, participants, including people with multiple sclerosis, had to learn lists of words that were either spoken or sung. Those who learned the sung words remembered them better because the rhythm and melody helped them remember more deeply and find the words again easily. Additionally, EEG data showed increased synchronization in the prefrontal cortex, particularly in alpha and beta brainwave activity, suggesting that music promotes neural plasticity and compensates for cognitive deficits.

These studies show that music dramatically impacts capacity for remembering words by facilitating intake, storage, and retrieval of information. Research by Ferreri and Verga (2016) and Thaut et al. (2014) indicates that the rhythm and melody in music help us think more deeply and remember words better. This effect is supported by neural evidence, showing increased prefrontal synchronization in alpha and beta brainwaves, which indicates music's role in promoting brain plasticity and compensation for deficits. These findings make music a potentially powerful tool for the enhancement of memory.

Alzheimer's and Music Therapy

Alzheimer's disease (AD) is a neurodegenerative disorder with a slow, insidious deterioration in cognition, impairment in memory, and change in behavior. It is pathologically characterized by the presence of amyloid-beta ($A\beta$) plaques and neurofibrillary tangles of hyperphosphorylated tau protein in the brain. These abnormalities cause impairment in neuronal function, and neuronal loss and brain atrophy follow. Etiology of AD is not clearly understood and is regarded to have a multi-factor etiology, with a role for both genetic, environmental, and life factors. The most important single risk factor is age, and most cases occur in persons over 65 years of age. Genetic factors, such as mutations in APP, PSEN1, and PSEN2, and carriage of the APOE ϵ 4 allele, have been associated with increased susceptibility. Environmental factors, such as cardiovascular disease, nutrition, and educational level, contribute to disease development and progression as well.

Music therapy is a therapeutic intervention utilizing music to promote care in an individual, both physically, emotionally, cognitively, and socially. It sometimes involves a therapeutic relationship with a trained music therapist and can include listening to music, singing, playing an instrument, and creating music. It seeks to promote improvement in health through taking advantage of the ubiquitous and accessible property of music. Music therapy, through studies, has been shown to have a beneficial role in improving mood, anxiety, and social behavior. On a neurological basis, music engages a variety of brain regions, including emotion, memory, and motor regions, and therefore, it is a powerful tool for rehabilitation and therapy.

In Alzheimer's disease, music therapy has been observed to have a range of cognitive, psychological, and behavior-related benefits. Cognitively, listening and taking part in music can stimulate recall, with memories for music having a propensity to outlast even in later disease phases. Stimulation can contribute to long-term cognitive function, continuity, and identity for the patient. Musical memory will survive even in later stages of AD, with patients recalling melody and lyrics when other forms of memory have failed them. This study concludes that music therapy can rekindle dormant cognitive processes, namely, episodic and procedural memory, less compromised in disease. Psychologically, music therapy lessens symptoms of depression and anxiety in AD patients. Music, and specifically, familiar tunes, can

evoke positive feelings, enhance mood, and calm tension. Besides, rhythmic and organized structures in them make them safer and included, and thus, patients are in a better state emotionally. Behaviorally, music therapy has been linked with a reduction in agitation, aggressiveness, and wandering, symptoms common in AD. According to the study, rhythmic stimulation through music can modulate function in terms of motion, and even social behavior. Besides, sessions in music therapy stimulate activity and engagement, and overall, a general improvement in wellbeing and interpersonal communication between carers, family, and patients.

Music Therapy and School-aged Children

Music therapy has emerged as a valuable intervention for enhancing cognitive and emotional development in school-aged children. Research indicates that the integration of music into educational settings can significantly benefit children's mental health and their learning outcomes. Foran (2009) stresses that music therapy for school-aged children, especially traumatized ones, can help them regulate their feelings, concentrate, and learn more. Children are able to improve concentration, control their emotions, and retain more information by listening to structured classical music, such as Mozart or Bach. Music therapy enhances cognitive skills, memory, and supports the emotional processing systems of the brain. This is particularly helpful in classrooms, enabling children with PTSD or learning challenges to focus and engage in tasks, which in turn enhances their overall academic and emotional outcomes.

In addition, Nie et al. (2022) investigated the impacts of musical training on auditory working memory in school-aged children whose native language was Chinese. The results indicated that, compared with children without such training, those who underwent musical training showed significant improvement in auditory working memory. The children who went through musical training, both instrumental and vocal, developed skills such as rhythm, pitch, and melody recognition. This training focused on enhancing auditory processing and memory through interactive, music-based activities, conducted over a period of time, typically lasting several months. This structured musical training was compared with other forms of intervention, such as second-language learning, to assess its specific impact on cognitive functions like memory. Improvements in working memory are especially important, as they facilitate key learning processes such as language acquisition and reading comprehension.

These studies elaborate on the different ways in which music therapy and musical interventions may be beneficial within educational settings. Music can be used in the curriculum for nurturing cognitive skills, emotional intelligence, and academic achievement among children.

Advocating for Music to be Incorporated into Schools

Integration of music within educational curricula is strongly supported by the increasing amount of research documenting numerous benefits of music in the cognitive, emotional, and social development of students. Thaut et al. (2014) examined the relevance of Neurologic Music Therapy (NMT) in the area of cognitive rehabilitation. Their research disclosed that NMT methods utilizing rhythm and melody to activate neural systems significantly improved attention, memory, and executive function. All this augurs quite well for the ability of organized musical interventions to support the cognitive processes fundamental to learning. These studies, therefore, collectively argue for the inclusion of music in educational settings, focusing on its role in increasing cognitive abilities, improving behavioral outcomes, and creating an enriched learning

environment. Music education can be a very important tool in fostering students' general development and academic achievement.

There are numerous ways in which music can be incorporated in schools, augmenting learning experiences for the students and fostering creativity. One such successful way is offering specialized music classes, e.g., general music for students in lower grades and specialized classes like band, choir, or orchestra for upper-grade students. Such programs allow students to develop musical competency, teamwork, and discipline. Additionally, music can be used in other subjects to aid learning; for example, teachers can use songs to teach multiplication tables, dates in history, or languages, making lessons more fun and memorable. Schools can also encourage musical involvement through performances and activities such as concerts, talent shows, and musicals, which provide students with the opportunity to showcase their talent and build confidence.

In addition to performances, the inclusion of music history and appreciation in the curriculum exposes students to different genres, cultures, and time periods, broadening their understanding of international traditions. Extracurricular music clubs, such as jazz bands, a cappella groups, and songwriting clubs, allow students to extend their musical experience outside of classroom hours while offering social affiliation. Additionally, technology can be utilized in music education to introduce students to digital music production, composition, and sound engineering to make music more accessible and also more relevant to today's world. Background music can also be utilized by educators in the classroom to enhance concentration, reduce stress, and ensure a good learning atmosphere. By integrating music into various aspects of schooling, schools can enrich students' school experiences, increase academic performance, and promote their creativity and emotional development.

Conclusion

The effect of music on memory is profound and intricate, offering significant benefits in cognitive enhancement, therapy, and learning. Research has shown that music can be used to improve auditory, visual, and verbal memory, as a training tool and memory prompt in a contextual environment. In therapy, music therapy has been shown to have excellent outcomes for patients with neurodegenerative diseases such as Alzheimer's, enhancing memory recall and emotional well-being. In educational settings, the integration of music into curricula and instruction has been shown to enhance cognitive ability, memory retention, and academic performance. However, these effects on memory can also be contingent upon a variety of individual traits such as familiarity, musical training, and individual interest. As more research continues to illuminate this relationship, it is clear that music has significant potential as an educational tool and cognitive aid. Adding music to schools and therapy can open new doors for improving memory, stimulating creativity, and improving overall cognitive health.

Limitations

While this review synthesizes a broad spectrum of studies examining the relationship between music and memory, several limitations must be acknowledged. First, the reviewed studies have a diverse set of methodologies, participant samples, and musical interventions, which complicates direct comparison and generalization. Variations in experiment design, sample size, and measurement procedures across different types of memory (short-term, long-term, working memory) give different results. Second, memory operational definitions and precise parameters for musical stimuli (tempo,

complexity, and familiarity) change considerably from one study to the next. Variability could puzzle our knowledge regarding how music influences memory recall and storage. Furthermore, individual differences, for example, with regard to music training background, cultural identity, and personal preference, also contribute to these effects but are not reliably controlled or explained in the literature. Most studies also use short-term intervention designs or laboratory settings, which may not capture the long-term implications or real-world applications of music in education and therapy. Finally, the risk of publication bias—i.e., the possibility that studies yielding positive findings will be more likely to be published—can skew the general perception of music's effect on memory. These constraints will need to be overcome in future research to create a fuller and more refined picture of the relationship between music and memory.

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